

Effect of cobalt doping on the structural, optical, thermal and mechanical properties of Ammonium Dihydrogen Phosphate single crystals

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Abstract:

Non linear optical single crystals of pure and Cobalt doped ADP were grown by slow evaporation solution growth technique at ambient temperature. The objective of the study is to find out the influence of cobalt on the growth morphology, optical and thermal characteristics of the ADP single crystals. The unit cell dimensions and crystalline nature of the grown crystals were verified by X-ray diffraction technique. The hardness of the crystals was determined by Vicker's Micro hardness test. The optical nature of the grown crystals was analyzed using the UV-Vis spectra. Thermo gravimetric analysis shows the thermal stability of the grown crystals. The addition of Cobalt impurity improves the quality, yield and growth rate of the ADP crystals. The optical quality, thermal and mechanical stability showed the suitability of the cobalt doped ADP crystals for optical applications.

Keywords: ADP, Doping, Cobalt, XRD, Micro hardness

References:

1. Z Delci, D Shyamala, S Karuna, A senthil and A Thayumanavan, Indian J. Appl. Phys. 51,(June,2013), pp. 426-430,
2. Beena M Amla and T Josephine Rani, Int. Journal of Research in Emerging Sci. & Tech, vol 2, 12(Dec 2015),
3. P. rajesh, A Silambarasan, P. Ramasamy, Material Research Bulletin 49(2014) 640-644,